

Insights into Prevalence of Diseases in Six Adopted Villages of VHMCH: Results from Medical Camps

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ABSTRACT: This survey aimed to determine the prevalence of diseases and the environmental status of six villages of Ellapuram block, Thiruvallur district, India. Two free medical camps were conducted in each village, and the most prevailing diseases were recorded. Poorivakkam had a population of 448 with a literacy rate of 73.46%, and osteoarthritis was the most prevalent disease at 25%. Akkarapakkam had a population of 1562 with a literacy rate of 79.53%, and osteoarthritis was also the most prevalent disease at 32.4%. Athivakkam had a population of 272 with a literacy rate of 87.55%, and lower respiratory tract infection was the most prevalent disease at 25%. Azhinjivakkam had a population of 1305 with a literacy rate of 86%, and osteoarthritis was again the most prevalent disease at 24%. Amindanallur had a population of 1018 with a literacy rate of 78.96% and osteoarthritis was most prevalent at 22%. Maduravasal had a population of 981 with a literacy rate of 68.91% with osteoarthritis as the most prevalent disease at 15%. The environmental status of all six villages was poor in terms of sanitation and solid waste disposal. The study emphasizes the need for improving nutrition, physical exercise, personal hygiene and sanitation in these villages to prevent the spread of diseases.

KEYWORDS: *Prevalence of diseases, Survey, Ellapuram block, Thiruvallur District, Community Medicine*

INTRODUCTION

Chronic diseases such as diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, chronic respiratory diseases, and cancer are becoming increasingly prevalent worldwide due to various factors such as aging population, lifestyle changes, and genetic predisposition. In rural areas, the

prevalence of chronic diseases can be affected by factors such as access to healthcare services, availability of healthy food options, and physical activity opportunities.

In order to determine the prevalence of chronic diseases in a specific village or region, it's important to conduct a survey that collects data on the health status and habits of the population. The data was analyzed to identify patterns and trends in the prevalence of chronic diseases and the risk factors associated with them. This information can be used to develop interventions and policies to improve the health outcomes of rural populations. The purpose of this survey/prevalence report is to assess the prevalence of chronic diseases and the environmental status of six adopted villages of Venkateswara Homoeopathic Medical College and Hospital, Chennai belonging to Ellapuram Block of Thiruvallur district, Tamil Nadu. The survey was conducted by organizing free medical camps in each of the six villages. The medical camps aimed to identify the most prevalent diseases in each village and provide remedial measures to prevent the spread of diseases. The survey also observed the environmental status of the, villages, including sanitation, solid waste disposal, toilet facilities and access to health care facilities. The report presents the findings from the medical camps conducted in the villages of Poorivakkam, Akkarapakkam, Athivakkam, Azhinjivakkam, Amindanallur, and Maduravasal.

The findings from the medical camps conducted in these villages highlight the need for better sanitation and personal hygiene practices in the region. The report recommends that the government and non-governmental organizations

work together to improve the environmental conditions and provide healthcare services to prevent the spread of diseases in these villages.

METHODS:

The study was conducted in six villages, namely Poorivakkam, Akkarapakkam, Athivakkam, Azhinjivakkam, Amindanallur, and Maduravasal, located in the rural areas of Ellapuram Tiruvallur district, Tamil nadu. The study aimed to assess the prevalence of various diseases among the population of these villages and their environmental status.

The study design was cross-sectional, and data were collected through free medical camps conducted in each of the six villages. The medical camps were conducted twice in each village, and patients who attended the camp were diagnosed and treated for their ailments with Homoeopathic medicines.

The medical camps were organized by a team of health care professionals, Homoeopathic doctors, interns, final year students belonging to Community Medicine Department of Venkateswara Homoeopathic Medical College and Hospital, Chennai in association with CRUSADE a nongovernmental organisation.. The camps were conducted in the local schools or community centres, and patients were given free HOMOEOPATHIC medications for their ailments.

During the medical camps, the demographic data of the patients, such as age, sex, and literacy rate, were recorded. The data on the prevalence of various diseases among the population were also collected. The most prevailing diseases in each village were identified, and remedial

measures were given to prevent the spread of these diseases.

The environmental status of each village was also assessed during the medical camps. Factors such as sanitation, drinking water source, toilet facility solid waste disposal, excreta disposal, and other environmental factors that contribute to the spread of diseases were observed and recorded.

The data collected from the medical camps were entered into a spreadsheet and analyzed using descriptive statistics. The prevalence of diseases in each village was calculated, and the most prevailing diseases were identified. The data on the environmental status of each village were also analyzed, and recommendations were made to improve the environmental conditions in these villages.

RESULTS:

The survey conducted in six villages provided valuable information about the prevalence of diseases and environmental status in these areas. The findings of the study are summarized below:

Poorivakkam:

Population: 448 (219 males, 229 females, and 41 children aged 0-6)

Literacy rate: 73.46%

Predominant diseases: Osteoarthritis (25%), Lower respiratory tract infection (20.4%), Spine disorders (17.9%), Diabetes mellitus (7.7%), Gastritis (10.7%), and others (18.4%)

Environmental status: Poor sanitation and open solid waste dumping.

Drinking water source. Wells and borewells of panchayat tank.

Toilet facility; 75% of the houses have toilet facility. The remaining population still uses fields for open defecation.

Schools: children study in the Government schools.

Total of 196 people participated in the study and were benefited from the camp.

Akkarapakkam:

Population: 1562 (750 males, 812 females, and 155 children aged 0-6)

Literacy rate: 79.53%

Predominant diseases: Osteoarthritis (32.4%), Lower respiratory tract infection

Figure 1: Prevalence of Disease - Poorivakkam

(19.10%), Hypertension (13.37%), Spine disorders (11.46%), Diabetes mellitus (8.2%), Gastritis (5.37%), and others (29.90%)

Environmental status: Poor sanitation and open solid waste dumping.

Drinking water source. Wells and borewells of panchayat tank.

Toilet facility; 65% of the houses have toilet facility. The remaining population still use fields for open defecation.

Schools: children study in the Government schools

Total of 157 people participated in the study and were benefited from the camp.

Figure 2: Prevalence of Diseases - Akkarapakkam

Athivakkam:

Population: 272 (139 males, 133 females, and 39 children aged 0-6)

Literacy rate: 87.55%

Predominant diseases: Lower respiratory tract infection (25%), Arthritis (21%), Spine disorders (18%), Hypertension (12%), Gastritis (6%), and others (19%)

Environmental status: Poor sanitation and open solid waste dumping.

Drinking water source. Wells and borewells of panchayat tank.

Toilet facility; 65% of the houses have toilet facility. The remaining population still uses fields for open defecation.

Schools: children study in the Government school
Total of 154 people participated in the study and were benefited from the camp.

Figure 3: Prevalence of Diseases - Athivakkam

Azhinjivakkam:

Population: 1305 (642 males, 663 females, and 112 children aged 0-6)

Literacy rate: 86%

Predominant diseases: Osteoarthritis (24%), Lower respiratory tract infection (21%), Hypertension (16%), Spine disorders (14%), Diabetes mellitus (9%), and others (16%)

Environmental status: Poor sanitation and open solid waste dumping .

Drinking water source. Wells and borewells of panchayat tank.

Toilet facility; 65% of the houses have toilet facility. The remaining population still uses fields for open defecation.

Schools: children study in the Government schools

Total of 188 people participated in the study and were benefited from the camp.

Figure 4: Prevalence of Diseases - Azhinjivakkam

Amindanallur:

Population: 1018 (531 males, 487 females, and 110 children aged 0-6)

Literacy rate: 78.96%

Predominant diseases: Osteoarthritis (22%), Lower respiratory tract infection (8%), Hypertension (13%) Spine disorders (16%), Diabetes mellitus (10%) and others (26%)

Environmental status: Poor sanitation and open solid waste dumping.

Drinking water source. Wells and bore wells of panchayat tank.

Toilet facility; 70% of the houses have toilet facility. The remaining population still uses fields for open defecation.

Schools: children study in the Government schools

Total of 177 people participated in the study and were benefited from the camp.

Figure 5: Prevalence of Diseases - Amindanallur

Maduravasal:

Population: 1305 (642 males, 663 females, and 112 children aged 0-6)

Literacy rate: 86%

Predominant diseases: Osteoarthritis (24%), Lower respiratory tract infection (21%), Hypertension (16%), Spine disorders (14%), Diabetes mellitus (9%), and others (16%)

Environmental status: Poor sanitation and open solid waste dumping.

Drinking water source. Wells and borewells of panchayat tank.

Toilet facility; 65% of the houses have toilet facility. The remaining population still uses fields for open defecation.

Schools: children study in the Government schools

Total of 103 people participated in the study and were benefitted from the camp.

Health care access: All the six villages have primary health centre located at Periyapalayam village which is approximately 5kms from each village.

Residents of the village are unable to access the primary health care for all their ailments despite the fact that government provides health care at free of cost.

Figure 6: Prevalence of Diseases - Maduravasal

DISCUSSION:

Based on the data collected from the survey conducted in six different villages, it is clear that there are several prevailing health issues that need attention. The survey was conducted through free medical camps that were organized in each of the villages. The total number of patients benefited from these camps in all villages is 981 and the most common health issues observed in each of the villages varied as well.

In Poorivakkam village, the most common health issues observed were osteoarthritis, lower respiratory tract infections, and spine disorders. Similarly, in Akkarapakkam village, the most common health issues were observed to be osteoarthritis, lower respiratory tract infections, and hypertension. In Athivakkam village, lower respiratory tract infections, arthritis, and spine disorders were the most common health issues observed. Finally, in Azhinjivakkam village, osteoarthritis, lower respiratory tract infections, and hypertension were found to be the most common health issues. In Amindanallur village the most prevalent disease was osteoarthritis followed by spine disorders and Hypertension. In Maduravasal village the most prevalent disease was osteoarthritis followed by lower respiratory tract infection and Hypertension.

From the data it is observed that females of age 40 years and above belonging to peri- & post-menopausal period with deficient nutrition whose occupation was predominantly as labourers, hence they are all affected with Osteoarthritis. These

issues were prevalent in every village surveyed, indicating a need for immediate attention and preventive measures. Other health issues, such as spine disorders, hypertension, arthritis, and gastritis, were also observed in some of the villages, but not in all.

In addition to the health issues, the survey also revealed that poor environmental conditions in the villages, such as sanitation and solid waste dumping, open defecation prevailed. This highlights the need for improving basic infrastructure and facilities in these villages to ensure better health outcomes for the residents.

In conclusion, the survey conducted in these six villages highlights the need for preventative measures and better infrastructure to improve the health outcomes of the residents. The data collected through the free medical camps can be used to develop targeted interventions and programs to address the prevalent health issues in each of the villages.

CONCLUSION:

Based on the data presented in the article, there are several remedial measures that can be implemented. These measures include:

- 1.Improve access to healthcare: Many individuals in low-income communities have limited access to healthcare, which makes it difficult for them to receive medical treatment when they become ill. Healthcare organizations should work to improve access to healthcare for these individuals by opening clinics in these communities and providing affordable medical care. Holistic approach with integrated health care facility can be made available to the community. Homeopathic cost effective treatment can be made more accessible and feasible to all the people in future.
- 2.School Health: School Health screening is being carried out as a part of village adoption activity. The survey recommends patronage of Government to permit School students to be covered and treated with Homoeopathic medicines as it is very beneficial and promotes growth

and development in growing children and assists in building immunity.

Above all, it is clear that the pandemic has had a significant impact on communities, particularly those that are already disadvantaged. However, by working together and implementing remedial measures, we can help mitigate the impact of the pandemic and support those who are most in need.

The free medical camp organized by VHMC at their door step was well received. Homoeopathic medicines which addresses the chronic diseases can improve their quality of life in the long run if taken regularly.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST:

There are no conflicts of interest.

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